

Different Interpretations of $\Delta E \Delta t \geq \hbar/2$? Part II

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The Heisenberg uncertainty relationship for $p-x$ and even forms for $E-t$ are based on variance which is an expectation value using W^* , W , where W is the wavefunction. We suggest that uncertainty is related to resolution and this may be washed out by using: $\int dx W^* \text{operator } W$. For example, $P(x) = 1/L \exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx)$ is a constant. It is sometimes suggested that this implies knowing p exactly, dictates that one does not know x at all. The point, we argue, however, is that even if p is exact, there is still a spatial resolution linked to \hbar/p , i.e. an uncertainty in x . The probabilistic view of quantum does not follow a particle in time and so one cannot know where it is. The $x-p$ Heisenberg uncertainty relation is a math statement which uses variance $\text{Var}(x)$, but for W^*W with many crests (as in the quantum oscillator case), there is average resolution for each crest and it is not clear why one would use the full $\text{Var}(x)$ as a measure of uncertainty in x .

Furthermore, the $x-p$ uncertainty relation is sometimes cited as explaining the existence of a nonzero ground state energy, but resolution arguments which do not use the uncertainty relation explain this as well.

The idea of resolution carries over to time, we argue. As a result, a bound state with $\exp(-iE_n t)$ has $P(t) = 1$, but $\exp(-iE_n t)$ implies a time resolution (or uncertainty) of \hbar/E_n . If one has a two energy level system: $W(x,t) = \exp(-iE_0 t) a_0(E_0) W_0(x) + \exp(-iE_1 t) a_1(E_1) W_1(x)$, then one may show that the interval $(0, T)$ where $T = \hbar/(E_1 - E_0)$ allows for $\exp(-iE_0 t)$ and $\exp(-iE_1 t)$ to be orthogonal. $E_1 - E_0$ describes the energy of a photon which raises E_0 to E_1 and this photon has a frequency $\exp(-i\omega t)$ such that $E_1 - E_0 = \hbar \omega$. As a result, there is a time resolution linked with the photon energy, but if E_0 and E_1 are very close in value, then the quantum system has an internal time resolution of the order $\hbar/E_0 \approx \hbar/E_1$.

Uncertainty type relations, where $\sqrt{\text{Var}(E)\text{Var}(t)} \geq \hbar/2$ or $\Delta t = \sqrt{\text{Var}(A)} / \langle dA/dt \rangle \rightarrow \Delta t \sqrt{\text{Var}(H)} \geq \hbar/2$ (1) seem to overlook the intrinsic time resolution \hbar/E which may lead to a much lower Δt .

Resolution Versus Variance in Position

Classical mechanics follows a particle in time so for a constant velocity: $x=vt$. Quantum mechanics, on the other hand, is probabilistic and is not necessarily involved with time. For example, a set of photons, all with the same p , sent at different times through a 2-slit apparatus (separation and slit widths of the order of \hbar/p) will produce an interference pattern. Time is not an issue. Thus, $\exp(ipx)$ is associated with a spatial resolution of:

$$\text{Spatial resolution} = \hbar/p \quad ((1))$$

This wavelength represents an uncertainty in space. That is why the photon (or electron etc) interferes when it reaches a 2-slit apparatus with spacings on the order of \hbar/p . The fact that $\exp(-ipx)\exp(ipx) = 1$ indicates that there is translational invariance. The usual interpretation, however, based on Heisenberg's $x-p$ uncertainty relation is that since p is exact, $\text{Var}(x)$ is

infinite, i.e.. one has no idea where the electron or photon is. We argue that it is the resolution \hbar/p that is important in a 2-slit interference situation, not the position of the photon or electron. The position of the electron is not needed to solve for the 2-slit interference pattern or for the reflection-refraction probabilities of one dimensional reflection-refraction. Resolution \hbar/p , however, is needed.

The x-p Heisenberg uncertainty principle follows from math (1) and does indeed give the relationship:

$$\sqrt{\text{Var}(p)\text{Var}(x)} \geq \hbar/2 \quad ((2))$$

This relationship is useful if the interpretation of $\text{Var}(x)$ is relevant. For example, for the ground state of a harmonic oscillator, W^*W has one crest and $\text{Var}(x)$ is linked to resolution in x. For higher energy levels, however, there are numerous crests in W^*W with differing heights and widths and it is not clear what the full $\text{Var}(x)$ represents physically, we argue. It seems better to calculate a $\text{Var}(x)$ for each crest because this yields the average x resolution at different positions of x. One could go further and take an average value of this to obtain one number, but this is not $\text{Var}(x)$, but average $\text{Var}(x)$ of a crest.

Thus, we suggest that x-resolution is key and not so much $\text{Var}(x)$.

Extension to Time

A bound state has an energy of E_n and a time wavefunction of $\exp(-iE_n t)$. There is a resolution in time given by:

$$\text{Time resolution} = \hbar/E_n \quad ((3))$$

We suggest that this time resolution should be of physical interest.

If this is the case, one may next consider a two energy level system:

$$W(x,t) = a_0(E_0) \exp(-iE_0 t) W_0(x) + a_1(E_1) \exp(-iE_1 t) W_1(x) \quad ((4))$$

If E_0 and E_1 are very close in value, then:

$$\hbar/E_0 \approx \hbar/E_1 \quad ((5))$$

This means that the intrinsic resolution is essentially \hbar/E_0 , we argue.

In order to create a Heisenberg-like uncertainty relation:

$$\sqrt{\text{Var}(E)\text{Var}(t)} \geq \hbar/2 \quad ((6))$$

which may be done mathematically, one needs a time range $(0, T)$ such that $\exp(-iE_0 t)$ and $\exp(-iE_1 t)$ are orthogonal in this range. Thus:

$$0 = \int_0^T \exp(iE_1 t) \exp(-iE_0 t) dt \rightarrow T = \hbar / (E_1 - E_0) \quad ((7))$$

If one calculates $\text{Var}(t)$, then first:

$$W^*(x,t)W(x,t) = a_0 a_0 W_0 W_0 + a_1 a_1 W_1 W_1 + 2 a_1 a_0 \cos((E_1 - E_0)t) W_1(x) W_0(x) \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{Integrating first over } x \text{ yields: } W^*(t)W(t) = a_0 a_0 + a_1 a_1 = 1 \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{Thus: } \text{Var}(t) = 1/T \int_0^T dt \, t^2 \text{ or } \text{Var}(x) = T^2/3 \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{Thus, there is a } t \text{ resolution of the order of: } \sqrt{\text{Var}(t)} = T \sqrt{1/3}, \text{ where } T = \hbar / (E_1 - E_0) \quad ((11))$$

An issue with ((11)), however, seems to be the following. If E_1 and E_0 are large and close in value, then $\hbar/E_0 \approx \hbar/E_1$ and this is a small number indicating a sharp t resolution. $E_1 - E_0$ on the other hand is a small number and so $\hbar/(E_1 - E_0)$ is a large number indicating a low t resolution. Given that the uncertainty relation approach is taken, i.e. ((11)), it seems that a low time resolution, namely that of the photon which excites E_0 to E_1 is considered, but the sharp t resolution of E_1 and E_2 are ignored. We suggest that they cannot be ignored.

We note that in (1), a different prescription than ((6)) is given for Δt , namely:

$$\Delta t = \sqrt{\text{Var}(A)} / \langle dA/dt \rangle \rightarrow \Delta t \sqrt{\text{Var}(H)} \geq \hbar/2$$

Here H is the Hamiltonian and A a time dependent operator such as a periodic time dependent potential variation to $V(x)$.

Out of curiosity, we note that if one takes $A = \sin(\omega t)$, where $\omega = (E_1 - E_0)/\hbar$ used above, then:

$$\langle dA/dt \rangle = \omega \langle A \rangle \text{ so } \Delta t = \hbar / (E_1 - E_0) \quad ((12))$$

((12)) is very similar to ((11)). Nevertheless, the resolutions of E_1 and E_0 , namely \hbar/E_0 and \hbar/E_1 are still being ignored.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in quantum mechanics, t and x resolutions are physically relevant. Quantum mechanics is probabilistic and so for $\exp(ipx)$, one does not follow a particle in time and doesn't know where it is. The key is that it has an x resolution or uncertainty of \hbar/p and this manifests itself experimentally in 2-slit interference etc. Thus, using $\exp(-ipx) \exp(ipx) = 1$ to calculate a variance bypasses this resolution altogether.

The Heisenberg x - p uncertainty relation is a math statement which may be useful if $\text{Var}(x)$ has meaning as it does in the ground state of a harmonic oscillator. For higher energy levels, there

are numerous crests in $W^*(x)W(x)$ and it is not clear why $\sqrt{\text{Var}(x)}$ should be important. Rather, the $\text{Var}(x)$ of each crest might be more relevant.

In the case of time, one may mathematically write a Heisenberg type uncertainty relation $\sqrt{\text{Var}(E)\text{Var}(t)} \geq \hbar/2$, if one has an interval $(0, T)$ in which various $\exp(-iEt)$ s are orthogonal. For two energy levels, this implies that $T = \hbar / (E_1 - E_0)$ and $\sqrt{\text{Var}(t)} = \sqrt{1/3} T$ where $T = \hbar / (E_1 - E_0)$. This, however, is the time resolution of a photon which would excite E_0 to E_1 . If E_0 and E_1 are large and approximately equal, this ignores the sharp time resolution $\hbar/E_0 \approx \hbar/E_1$ which we argue should be important.

Even if one uses a different E-t uncertainty prescription such as: $\Delta t = \sqrt{\text{Var}(A)} / \langle dA/dt \rangle \rightarrow \Delta t \sqrt{\text{Var}(H)} \geq \hbar/2$ from ((1)), for $A = \sin(\omega t)$ with $\omega = (E_1 - E_0)/\hbar$, one obtains $\Delta t = \hbar / (E_1 - E_0)$ which again bypasses the resolutions \hbar/E_0 and \hbar/E_1 .

References

1. Rais, J. and van Hees, H. and Greiner, C. Bound State Formation in Time Dependent Potentials (2022) <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2207.04898>